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compounds were assigned on the basis of elemental analysis, ir, pmr and mass spectral data.

Scheme 2. Reagents: (i) CS_2 , liq. N^+I_3 , $ClCH_2COONa$, NH_2NH_2 , (ii) $RCHO$.

Synthesis of some New Thiosemicarbazides and Thiosemicarbazones as Possible Antitubercular and Antibacterial Agents

DEEPA VANUGOPAL, DEEPTI PANDYA
and
K. B. NAIK*

Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science,
M. S. University of Baroda, Baroda-390 002

Manuscript received 25 November 1988, revised 7 March 1989,
accepted 9 March 1989

THIOSEMICARBAZIDES and thiosemicarbazones are associated with broad spectrum biological activities¹. The present work is undertaken with a view to synthesise compounds having better biological properties. Some dithiosemicarbazones were synthesised by reaction of 4,4'-diaminobiphenylmethane (1) with 4,4'-diaminobiphenyl ether (4) via dithiosemicarbazides with aromatic aldehydes (Schemes 1 and 2). The structures of the

Scheme 1. Reagents: (i) CS_2 , liq. NH_3 , $ClCH_2COONa$, NH_2NH_2 , (ii) $RCHO$.

Experimental

M.p.s are uncorrected. Microanalysis was performed on a Coleman instrument. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu 408 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 (90 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard.

4,4'-Di(3-thiosemicarbazide)biphenylmethane (2): A mixture of 4,4'-diaminobiphenylmethane (0.01 mol), ethanol (30 ml) and NH_4OH (20 ml) was cooled below 30° and carbon disulphide (8 ml) added slowly during 15 min with shaking and then allowed to stand for 1 h. Sodium monochloroacetate (0.02 mol) was added to it followed by the addition of 50% hydrazine hydrate (14 ml). The reaction mixture was concentrated to half of its volume and allowed to stand overnight. The resulting thiosemicarbazide was crystallised from DMF, (69%), m.p. 194° (Found: C, 52.50; H, 5.51; N, 24.03. $C_{14}H_{16}N_6S_2$ requires: C, 52.02; H, 5.20; N, 24.27%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3360–3330 ($N-H$) and 1110 cm^{-1} ($C=S$); δ (DMSO) 3.9 (2H, s, CH_2), 7.1–7.6 (8H, m, Ar), 9.65 (4H, br, NH); m/z 314 ($M^+ - N_2H_4$), 282 ($M^+ - 2N_2H_4$), 272 ($M^+ - C(=S) - NHNH_2$) and 240 ($272 - N_2H_4$).

4,4'-Di(3-thiosemicarbazide)biphenyl ether (5): It was synthesised by following the method described above, and the product crystallised from DMF-water, (71%), m.p. $197-98^\circ$ (Found: C, 48.76; H, 4.71; N, 23.66. $C_{14}H_{16}N_6S_2O$ requires: C, 48.27; H, 4.59; N, 24.10%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3300–3200 ($N-H$) and 1190 cm^{-1} ($C=S$); δ (DMSO) 7.10–7.85 (8H, m, Ar), 9.25 (4H, br, NH); m/z 316 ($M^+ - N_2H_4$), 284 ($M^+ - 2N_2H_4$), 274 ($M^+ - C(=S) - NHNH_2$) and 242 ($274 - N_2H_4$).

4,4'-Di(substituted-benzaldehyde-3-thiosemicarbazone)biphenylmethane (3): A mixture of 2 (0.01 mol) and aromatic aldehyde (0.02 mol) was refluxed in ethanol (95%; 50 ml) for 2 h. The reaction

mixture allowed to stand overnight at room temperature. The resulting solid product was dried and

TABLE I - PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3 AND 6*

Compd. no.	R	M.p.**	Yield %	Mol. formula
3a	C ₆ H ₅	165 ^a	80	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ S ₂
3b	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	193 ^b	71	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ N ₂ S ₂
3c	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	157 ^a	76	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ N ₂ S ₂ O ₂
3d	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	210 ^a	74	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₂ S ₂ O ₄
3e	<i>o</i> -Cl-C ₆ H ₄	198 ^a	71	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₂ S ₂ Cl ₂
3f	<i>m</i> -Br-C ₆ H ₄	232 ^b	73	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₂ S ₂ Br ₂
6a	C ₆ H ₅	205 ^b	73	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ S ₂ O
6b	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	159 ^a	75	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ N ₂ S ₂ O ₂
6c	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	155 ^a	76	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ N ₂ S ₂ O ₂
6d	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	233 ^a	74	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₂ S ₂ O ₄
6e	<i>o</i> -Cl-C ₆ H ₄	211 ^a	76	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₂ S ₂ OCl ₂
6f	<i>m</i> -Br-C ₆ H ₄	236 ^b	71	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₂ S ₂ OBr ₂

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

**Crystallisation solvent; ^apyridine-water, DMF-water.

crystallised from proper solvent. 4,4'-Di(substituted-tolualdehyde-3-thiosemicarbazone)biphenylmethane (3c): ν_{max} 3 300 (NH), 1 510 (C=N) and 1 190 cm⁻¹ (C=S); δ (DMSO) 3.8 (6H, s, CH₃), 4.0 (2H, s, CH₂), 6.9-7.95 (OH, m, 16H Ar + 4NH) and 8.1 (2H, s, CH). 4,4'-Di(substituted-tolualdehyde-3-thiosemicarbazone)biphenyl ether (6c): ν_{max} (KBr) 3 300 (NH), 1 510 (C=N) and 1 190 cm⁻¹ (C=S); δ (DMSO) 3.6 (6H, s, CH₃), 7.15-8.0 (20H, m, 16H Ar + 4NH) and 8.3 (2H, s, CH).

Biological activity: Compounds 2, 4, 3b, 3f, 6c, 6d were tested for antitubercular activity in DMF solvent *in vitro* against the human virulent strain of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (H₃₇R₀) by serial dilution method. 2 was active at 3.12 μ g ml⁻¹ concentration, 4, 3b, 6c and 6d were found to be active at 25 μ g ml⁻¹ and 3f was found to be active at 50 μ g ml⁻¹ concentration.

Compounds 4, 3d, 6b and 6c were tested for antibacterial activity. None of the compounds tested (MIC in 100 μ g ml⁻¹) was found to have antibacterial activity.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Prof. P. K. Bhattacharya, Head of Chemistry Department for facilities and encouragement, to Dr. D. E. Fenton of Sheffield University for mass spectra, to Mr. Madhava Rao and Mrs. Sushila Amin for ir and nmr spectra. The authors are thankful to Prof. P. J. Dave, Head of Microbiology Department, M. S. University, Dr. B. J. Khadse, Head of Chemotherapy Department, Haffkine Institute, Bombay for biological screening and to Dr. V. K. Singh for help. One of the authors (D. V.) thanks U.G.C., New Delhi for financial assistance.

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Synthesis of Novel Analogs of Phthalein Dyes with a Chiral Carbon Atom

SHER ALI*

Department of Chemistry, University of Garhwal,
Tehri Campus, Tehri-249 001

and

I. M. BEG

Department of Chemistry, Dayanand Vedic
(P. G.) College, Ora-285 001

and

P. C. GUPTA

Department of Chemistry, University of Allahabad,
Allahabad-211 002

Manuscript received 14 June 1988, revised 16 January 1989,
accepted 21 February 1989

DIFFERENT 2-arylbenzoic acids are γ -keto acids of aromatic series and exist in equilibrium as ring-chain tautomers¹. The existence of ring tautomer creates the possibility of condensing it with different phenols to give novel phthalein analogues with a chiral carbon atom. A number of phthalein analogues with a chiral carbon atom have been obtained by condensing 2-benzoyl-3-nitrobenzoic acid with various phenols-aromatic hydroxy compounds.

Results and Discussions

2-Benzoyl-3-nitro-benzoic acid (1) and 2-*p*-toluyl-3-nitrobenzoic acid (2) were prepared with the help of Friedel-Crafts reaction by using nitrophthalic anhydride to react with benzene and toluene respectively in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride. The acids have been found to exist as a mixture of ring-chain tautomers as evidenced by the spectral data: 1, ν_{max} (KBr) 1 660 (C=O diaryl ketone), 1 695 (C=O), 1 745 (C=O lactonic), 2 650w (OH carboxyl) and 3 500 cm⁻¹ (OH lactol); δ (CHCl₃) 1.85-2.05 (3H, m, nitro-ring protons), 2.3-2.95 (5H, m, ring protons) and 4.25 (1H, s, lactol proton); 2, ν_{max} (KBr) 1 682 (C=O diaryl ketone), 1 710 (C=O), 1 735 (C=O lactonic), 2 600w (OH carboxyl) and 3 100 cm⁻¹ (OH lactol); (CHCl₃) 1.90-2.05 (3H, m, nitro-ring protons), 2.25-2.85 (4H, m, methyl ring proton), 7.55 (3H, s, CH₃) and 4.35 (1H, s, lactol proton).

Different analogs of phthaleins (4a-h and 5a-h) have been prepared (Table 1) by condensing